

Abstract

Five Animal Qigong (Wu Qin Xi) for Children's Wellbeing.

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Abstract

This systematic review investigates the impact of *Wu Qin Xi*, a *Qigong* practice, on the health and well-being of children. Drawing from the principles of Traditional Chinese Medicine and attributed to the ancient physician *Hua Tuo*, *Wu Qin Xi* uses movements inspired by animals to foster a connection with natural forces for therapeutic purposes. The well-being of children is influenced by a range of elements, including their physical activity, nutritional intake, and mental health. We conducted a systematic search of several databases, identifying eight studies that met our criteria for exploring the effects of *Wu Qin Xi* on children's health. The findings suggest encouraging benefits of *Wu Qin Xi* for pediatric health. Specifically, children with autism spectrum disorder showed improvements in behaviour and sensory processing, while those with asthma experienced enhanced lung function and a better quality of life. For children with lobar pneumonia, *Wu Qin Xi* was associated with improved pulmonary function and shorter hospitalisations. The technique also demonstrated benefits for children with spinal abnormalities, leading to improved mobility and posture. Furthermore, *Wu Qin Xi* appeared to reduce stress and enhance cognitive function. It is important to note, however, that the studies reviewed had some limitations, including small sample sizes and varied intervention methods. *Wu Qin Xi* shows potential as a complementary treatment for various childhood conditions. Nevertheless, more rigorous research, including studies with larger participant groups and improved designs, is needed to confirm its effectiveness thoroughly.

Keywords: *Qigong*; Five Animal *Qigong*; *Wu Qin Xi*; Wellbeing; Children.

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